

ON THE INCREASE OF REINFORCEMENT

DUCTILITY DUE TO COMPOSITION

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Abstract

It has been reported in several papers that even a brittle fiber might exhibit a ductile behavior for tension when it would be once embedded into a matrix having larger elongation than that of the fiber [1] [2].

As for such phenomena, the author has conducted two kinds of experiments. The first one has been done with a unidirectionally solidified eutectic alloy Si-Al₃Ni-Al and the results have already been reported in the reference [3]. In this case, Si and Al₃Ni whiskers showed very large deflections together with Al-matrix without fracture. As the second one, the author presents in this paper the tension test results with the Aluminum 7075C-T6 plates / Epoxy laminates which exhibited larger elongations than those of monolithic aluminum plates. These phenomena represent the merit of composition for the revolution of material behavior including improvement of mechanical properties.

1. Introduction

Most reinforcing fibers widely used in composites, for example, such as glass-, boron-, carbon-, SiC- or metal-fibers exhibit brittle properties for tension. The fact that if even such brittle fibers are once embedded into a matrix having larger elongation than that of the fibers, they will exhibit necking phenomena or large elongations up to fracture for tension has been known.

For example, D.L. McDanel et al [1] found that the tungsten fibers elongated inside a copper matrix as like as wheat gluten candy bars under tension, although they were essentially very brittle in air. J. Mullin et al [2] reported the necking of boron fibers took place in an epoxy resin matrix. Multiple necking phenomena of fibers have been reported.

As for such phenomena, the present author et al have conducted the compression tests with a unidirectionally solidified eutectic alloy : Si-Al₃Ni-Al and reported in the paper [3]. For reference, some of the results are reproduced in Fig. 1. Two cylindrical compression test specimens of 6 mm in diameter and 10 mm in length were made from Si-Al₃Ni-Al where the

Fig.1 Compression failure of round bar specimens made of unidirectionally solidified Si-Al₃Ni-Al eutectic alloy.

- (a) Cut section of a fractured specimen
- (b) "Brooming" at the upper end
- (c) Shear fracture accompanied by bending deformations of Si and Al₃Ni whiskers.

The whisker-like gray fibers are Si and white ones are Al₃Ni. The volume fractions of Si and Al₃Ni are 12.9% and 8.1%, respectively.

axial directions were parallel to the whiskers of Si and Al₃Ni. Those specimens were subjected to axial compression under flat-end conditions at their both ends. In Fig. 1 the vertical direction is their axial direction. Fig. 1 (a) shows a section of a fractured specimen which was cut axially after test. Fig. 1 (b) shows a so-called "brooming deformation" caused at the upper end of the specimen. Fig. 1 (c) is a close-up view showing the shear deformation coupled with bending deformation in a specimen. These figures indicate that the remarkably large bending deformations of Si and Al₃Ni whiskers could be possible without fracture inside of aluminum matrix, although they were brittle in air. The reason why such large deformations could be possible is reduced to the excellent bonding between Si and Al₃Ni whiskers and aluminum matrix.

2. Tension Test of 7075C-T6 Aluminum Plates / Epoxy Laminates

In order to investigate the bonding effect on the elongation from the other point of view, the author has recently conducted tension test with the laminates of Epoxy-bonded 7075C-T6 Aluminum Plates. These tension test pieces were fabricated by Epoxy Film bonding of 7075C-T6 Aluminum sheets, designated as AI, which were carefully machined into dumbbell type with 40 mm wide and 150 mm long parallel part in advance before bonding process. Each sheet of AI was 1 mm thick.

Fig. 2 gives the designation and size of test specimens. L II, L III and L IV are the laminates of two, three and four plies of 7075C-T6 Aluminum sheet, AI, respectively. These laminates are approximately 2.2, 3.5 and

Fig.2 Designation and size of specimens.

4.8 mm thick. For comparison, 7075C-T6 monolithic plates of 2 and 3 mm thickness were also prepared, being denoted as A II and A III respectively. All of these specimens from A I to L IV had the same plan form of dumbbell type and no cut-outs or notches on the sides surfaces. Number of each test specimen was four.

Fig. 3 Stress-strain curves for each specimen.

For bonding, the modified epoxy resin film, "Scotch Weld AF126-2," was used. After the surface treatment of aluminum sheets, AI, by primer, "EC2320," the above resin films were put between each AI sheet, pressed with the pressure of 2.8 kgf/cm^2 (2.8 atmospheric pressure) and heated and cured in an auto-clave under the condition of temperature $131 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ for 60 minutes. The above molding process was very carefully conducted not so as to make any scratch on specimens.

On the surfaces of each specimen, the gage marks were drawn in every 10 mm distance before test. Fig. 3 gives the nominal stress vs nominal strain curves for each specimen measured under quasi-static loading, i.e. with the test strain speed of 0.3%/sec for elastic range and 500 μ /sec for inelastic range.

Fig.4 Elongation λ in % vs thickness of monolithic single plates and laminates.

O : Monolithic Plates
 Δ : Laminated Plates

The elongations, designated by λ , were measured as follows. Since the fracture did not always occur at the midsection of test pieces, we selected the two gage marks, say A and B, among the drawn marks before test, where the distance between A and B was originally l , and taken so as to put the fractured section at or close to the midpoint of AB as far as possible. Then we measured the elongated distance AB, calculated the elongation Δl and obtained the elongation (Strain) $\lambda = \Delta l / l$. According to the specimen size used in test, we have taken $l=50 \text{ mm}$. Fig. 4 shows the plots of the % elongation λ vs the thickness of laminates and monolithic single plates. From this figure we can find remarkable differences of elongations ranging from 10 to 20%. The laminates have 10 to 20% larger elongations up to fracture than those of the corresponding monolithic plates. It is expected that such increase of elongation will come from the constraint action of epoxy bond layers for deformation of each aluminum ply sheet.

3. Conclusion

The test result on an eutectic alloy mentioned above represents how the whiskers can have the large flexibility inside a ductile matrix. The latter example of laminated plated shows the larger elongation than that of the monolithic plates. This shows not only a merit of lamination, but also suggests a potential for improvement of material behavior by means of composition.

References

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